

Annex to:

EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), Costa G, Di Piazza G, Koevoets P, Iacono G, Liebana E, Pasinato L, Rizzi V, Rossi M, 2022. Guidelines for reporting Whole Genome Sequencing-based typing data through the EFSA One Health WGS System. EFSA supporting publication 2022:EN-7413. 29 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7413.

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Annex C – Examples of JSON format for programmatic submission to the EFSA One Health WGS System of Experimental, Typing and Epidemiological dataset by the Data Provider

When submitting data to EFSA One Health WGS database programmatically, users are always requested to submit both Experimental and Typing data at the same time. The submission of Epidemiological data is optional.

1. Experimental data

Below an example of JSON file for submitting Experimental data related to paired-end sequence reads of an *Escherichia coli* isolate (see Table 4 in the main text). Mandatory elements are in bold, optional elements are in *Italics*. If an element is mandatory according to conditions explained in "Guidelines for reporting Whole Genome Sequencing-based typing data through the EFSA One Health WGS System", the element is underlined.

```
{
  "localRawReadId": "test2345235",
  "instrumentModelCode": null,
  "serotypeId": null,
  "isolateSpecieCode": "RF-00003072-PAR",
  "libraryLayoutCode": 2,
  "fastQ1FileName": "test_1.fq.gz",
  "fastQ1Md5": "a4d7caca033ed44ef6c787c2b98339fa",
  "fastQ2FileName": "test_2.fq.gz",
  "fastQ2Md5": "9a8564f91378f8b3c3a992f7c0fd4f89",
}
```

2. Typing data

Typing data are composed by two files:

- a JSON file including quality check measures and *in silico* typing data other than the cgMLST profile
- A Tab Separated Values (TSV)- formatted file including the cgMLST allelic profile.

A.1.1. JSON file including quality check measures and *in silico* typing data

Below an example of JSON file including the elements related to the submission of *Escherichia coli* with Local Raw Reads ID "test2345235" (as in the example presented in point 1). Mandatory elements are in bold, optional elements are in *Italics*. If an element is mandatory according to conditions explained in "Guidelines for reporting Whole Genome Sequencing-based typing data through the EFSA One Health WGS System", the element is underlined.

```
{ "localRawReadsID": "test2345235",
  "QualityCheck": {
    "Fastq": {
      "ReadMeanLength": 195,
      "Q30Rate": 0.9,
      "TotalBases": 415977560
    },
  },
}
```

```

"AssemblyQualityStatistics": {
  "AssemblyCoverage": 61,
  "AssemblyStatistics": {
    "N50Contigs": 151881,
    "GenomeSize": 5421454,
    "NumberOfContigs": 345
  }
},
"Results": {
  "PredictedSerotype": {
    "Serotype": "O157:H7",
    "Software": "seq_typing"
  },
  "PredictedPathotype": {
    "Pathotype": "STEC",
    "VeroToxin": {
      "VT1Positive": true,
      "VT2Positive": true
    },
    "AdhesionGenes": {
      "eaePositive": true,
      "aatPositive": false,
      "aggRPositive": false,
      "aaiCPositive": false
    },
    "Software": "patho_typing",
    "GeneList": [
      {
        "GeneName": "stx1a",
        "Identity": "100.0",
        "Coverage": "99.68"
      },
      {
        "GeneName": "stx1b",
        "Identity": "100.0",
        "Coverage": "100.0"
      },
      {
        "GeneName": "stx2a",
        "Identity": "100.0",
        "Coverage": "99.06"
      },
      {
        "GeneName": "stx2b",
        "Identity": "100.0",
        "Coverage": "95.93"
      },
      {
        "GeneName": "eae",
        "Identity": "72.91",
        "Coverage": "92.7"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```



```
"SampleData": {
  "sampling_local_id": "Sample12345",
  "programme_type_id": null,
  "programme_info_id": null,
  "sampler_id": "CX02A",
  "sampling_point_id": "E520A",
  "sampling_country_id": "IT",
  "sampling_country_origin_id": null,
  "sampling_area_id": null,
  "sampling_year": 2019,
  "sampling_month": null,
  "sampling_day": null,
  "sampling_matrix_code": "A06HL#F04.A0EZH",
  "sampling_matrix_free_text": "Brazil nuts from brand NUTS"
},
"IsolateData": {
  "isolation_local_id": "Isolate12345",
  "isolation_year": null,
  "isolation_month": null,
  "isolation_day": null
}
}
```